

Table 1. Characteristics of Included Studies (n=12)

Author(s)	Year	Country	Study Design	Sample Size
Alquraini et al. [10]	2015	Saudi Arabia	Reliability Study	100 nurses
Taheri et al. [11]	2015	Iran	Cross-sectional	150 nurses
Li et al. [12]	2018	China	Meta-analysis	N/A
Hardy & Calleja [13]	2018	Australia	Scoping Review	N/A
Bijani & Khaleghi [14]	2019	Iran	Qualitative	20 nurses
Duko et al. [15]	2019	Ethiopia	Cross-sectional	150 nurses
Reay et al. [16]	2019	Canada	Qualitative	25 nurses
Rosenberg [17]	2019	USA	Review	N/A
Delmas et al. [18]	2020	France	Quasi-experimental	30 nurses
Salifu et al. [19]	2022	Ghana	Mixed-methods	40 nurses
Soola et al. [20]	2022	Iran	Cross-sectional	200 nurses
Al-Thobaity et al. [21]	2024	Saudi Arabia	Qualitative	50 nurses
Ouellet et al. [22]	2025	Canada	Systematic Review	N/A